

Leiden Manifesto as a Consumer Label?

Lorna Elizabeth Wildgaard, Assistant professor, University of Copenhagen

Heidi Holst Madsen, Information specialist, Royal Danish Library

Marianne Gauffriau, Special adviser, Royal Danish Library

January 18

**DET KGL.
BIBLIOTEK**

Royal Danish Library

Background: Implementation of Leiden Manifesto (LM)

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

Loughborough
University

INDIANA UNIVERSITY
BLOOMINGTON

GHENT
UNIVERSITY

**DET KGL.
BIBLIOTEK**
Royal Danish Library

Københavns Universitetsbibliotek

January 18

LM as a consumer label

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size 8 fl oz	
Serving Per Container 1	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 150	Calories from Fat 70
% Daily Values*	
Total Fat 8g	12%
Saturated Fat 5g	25%
Trans Fat 0g	
Cholesterol 35mg	12%
Sodium 120mg	5%
Total Carbohydrate 11g	4%
Dietary Fiber 0g	0%
Sugars 12g	
Protein 8g	16%
* Percent Daily Values are based on a 2,000 calorie diet.	

Consumer label from: Clare, G. P. & Burghardt, K. Getting the Message: Front of Package Labeling. *Management*, 4(5): 112-122 (2014)

LM as a consumer label

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size 8 fl oz	
Serving Per Container 1	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 150	Calories from Fat 70
% Daily Values*	
Total Fat 8g	12%
Saturated Fat 5g	25%
Trans Fat 0g	
Cholesterol 35mg	12%
Sodium 120mg	5%
Total Carbohydrate 11g	4%
Dietary Fiber 0g	0%
Sugars 12g	
Protein 8g	16%

*Percent Daily Values are based on a 2,000 calorie diet.

Leiden Manifesto: Ten principles to guide quantitative research evaluation	Assessment
1) Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment The bibliometric analysis is included in a CV and publication track record in a research application. The application will be evaluated by a panel of researchers from the health sciences.	
2) Measure performance against the research missions of the institution, group or researcher The indicators were not linked to an explicit research mission. According to the instructions for applicants, bibliometric indicators are not mandatory but may be included. No specific indicators are mentioned. The overall evaluation criterion is scientific excellence. In the health sciences, the h-index, number of publications and citations are often presented in a CV and may be seen as an implicit standard for showing impact, and together with other information indicate excellence.	
3) Protect excellence in locally relevant research Not relevant as the research area of Prof. NN and the application is international.	-
4) Keep data collection and analytical processes open, transparent and simple The analysis is developed in collaboration with Prof. NN and all indicators are known by the health sciences research community.	
5) Allow those evaluated to verify data and analysis The analysis is verified by Prof. NN.	
6) Account for variation by field in publication and citation practices The analysis does not support comparisons with other research fields, e.g. by showing field-normalized indicators or including indicators often used by other research fields.	
7) Base assessment of individual researchers on a qualitative judgement of their portfolio See principle 1.	
8) Avoid misplaced concreteness and false precision The analysis presents multiple indicators to give a pluralistic picture of Prof. NN's performance. The data set for the analysis is developed in collaboration with Prof. NN to ensure the best possible coverage.	
9) Recognize the systemic effects of assessment and indicators The analysis presents multiple indicators and not the h-index alone which is often seen in health sciences.	
10) Scrutinize indicators regularly and update them See principle 9.	

Evaluation example 1

3) Protect excellence in locally relevant research

The analysis includes non-English publications but does not use metrics built on high-quality non-English publications that would serve to identify excellence in locally relevant research.

Evaluation example 2

5) Allow those evaluated to verify data and analysis
The analysis is verified by the department.

LM as a consumer label

Nutrition Facts	
Serving Size 8 fl oz	
Serving Per Container 1	
Amount Per Serving	
Calories 150	Calories from Fat 70
% Daily Values*	
Total Fat 8g	12%
Saturated Fat 5g	25%
Trans Fat 0g	
Cholesterol 35mg	12%
Sodium 120mg	5%
Total Carbohydrate 11g	4%
Dietary Fiber 0g	0%
Sugars 12g	
Protein 8g	16%

*Percent Daily Values are based on a 2,000 calorie diet.

Leiden Manifesto: Ten principles to guide quantitative research evaluation	Assessment
1) Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment The bibliometric analysis is included in a CV and publication track record in a research application. The application will be evaluated by a panel of researchers from the health sciences.	
2) Measure performance against the research missions of the institution, group or researcher The indicators were not linked to an explicit research mission. According to the instructions for applicants, bibliometric indicators are not mandatory but may be included. No specific indicators are mentioned. The overall evaluation criterion is scientific excellence. In the health sciences, the h-index, number of publications and citations are often presented in a CV and may be seen as an implicit standard for showing impact, and together with other information indicate excellence.	
3) Protect excellence in locally relevant research Not relevant as the research area of Prof. NN and the application is international.	-
4) Keep data collection and analytical processes open, transparent and simple The analysis is developed in collaboration with Prof. NN and all indicators are known by the health sciences research community.	
5) Allow those evaluated to verify data and analysis The analysis is verified by Prof. NN.	
6) Account for variation by field in publication and citation practices The analysis does not support comparisons with other research fields, e.g. by showing field-normalized indicators or including indicators often used by other research fields.	
7) Base assessment of individual researchers on a qualitative judgement of their portfolio See principle 1.	
8) Avoid misplaced concreteness and false precision The analysis presents multiple indicators to give a pluralistic picture of Prof. NN's performance. The data set for the analysis is developed in collaboration with Prof. NN to ensure the best possible coverage.	
9) Recognize the systemic effects of assessment and indicators The analysis presents multiple indicators and not the h-index alone which is often seen in health sciences.	
10) Scrutinize indicators regularly and update them See principle 9.	

Pilot project: 2 cases

Dept. of Forensic Medicine (DFM)

- Analyzing department-level publication output, collaborators, and impact.

Professor Thorkild I. A. Sørensen (TIAS)

- Analyzing publication output and impact.

Source:

<http://maxpixel.freegreatpicture.com/Business-Feedback-Opinion-Group-Communication-2044702>

Pilot project evaluation method

Department of Forensic Medicine

- More interested in the bibliometric analysis
- The consumer label is an instruction sheet for bibliometricians, less relevant to the client
- Awareness of the shortcomings the bibliometric analysis in regards to principle 3 was relevant & valuable (Protect excellence in locally relevant research)

Leiden Manifesto: Ten principles to guide quantitative research evaluation	Assessment
1) Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment The bibliometric analysis is part of the background information for the department's self-evaluation report and the external peer review panel's report.	
2) Measure performance against the research missions of the institution, group or researcher The analysis design from last year's SUND Health Report was kept. Neither SUND nor the bibliometricians have updated the design according to the focus areas of the protocol for the research evaluation.	
3) Protect excellence in locally relevant research The analysis includes non-English publications but does not use metrics built on high-quality non-English publications that would serve to identify excellence in locally relevant research.	
4) Keep data collection and analytical processes open, transparent and simple All datasets and sub-analyses are available to the department. The majority of the indicators are simple. Two indicators (Share of 10% highly cited publications and BFI) are explained to help non-bibliometricians understand the indicators.	
5) Allow those evaluated to verify data and analysis The analysis is verified by the department.	
6) Account for variation by field in publication and citation practices The first part of the analysis is based on CURIS which includes all research publications authored by the department. This part of the analysis shows journal publications, books and contributions to books. The second part of the analysis is based on SciVal and includes 89% of the journal publications from CURIS. The indicators Share of 10% highly cited publications and BFI can be used across research fields.	
7) Base assessment of individual researchers on a qualitative judgement of their portfolio Not relevant as the analysis is carried out at department level.	—
8) Avoid misplaced concreteness and false precision The analysis presents multiple indicators to give a pluralistic picture of the department. All indicators are presented as integers, bars, or dots. Still, small variations from one year to the next year should not be interpreted as an increase or decline.	
9) Recognize the systemic effects of assessment and indicators The analysis presents multiple indicators without highlighting any of them, and the analysis design was introduced in 2015 without any links to an incentive structure.	
10) Scrutinize indicators regularly and update them See principle 2.	

Professor Thorkild I. A. Sørensen

—Was very interested in understanding and discussing the principles

—Thought the consumer label enriched the bibliometric analysis

Leiden Manifesto: Ten principles to guide quantitative research evaluation	Assessment
1) Quantitative evaluation should support qualitative, expert assessment The bibliometric analysis is included in a CV and publication track record in a research application. The application will be evaluated by a panel of researchers from the health sciences.	
2) Measure performance against the research missions of the institution, group or researcher The indicators were not linked to an explicit research mission. According to the instructions for applicants, bibliometric indicators are not mandatory but may be included. No specific indicators are mentioned. The overall evaluation criterion is scientific excellence. In the health sciences, the h-index, number of publications and citations are often presented in a CV and may be seen as an implicit standard for showing impact, and together with other information indicate excellence.	
3) Protect excellence in locally relevant research Not relevant as the research area of Prof. NN and the application is international.	—
4) Keep data collection and analytical processes open, transparent and simple The analysis is developed in collaboration with Prof. NN and all indicators are known by the health sciences research community.	
5) Allow those evaluated to verify data and analysis The analysis is verified by Prof. NN.	
6) Account for variation by field in publication and citation practices The analysis does not support comparisons with other research fields, e.g. by showing field-normalized indicators or including indicators often used by other research fields.	
7) Base assessment of individual researchers on a qualitative judgement of their portfolio See principle 1.	
8) Avoid misplaced concreteness and false precision The analysis presents multiple indicators to give a pluralistic picture of Prof. NN's performance. The data set for the analysis is developed in collaboration with Prof. NN to ensure the best possible coverage.	
9) Recognize the systemic effects of assessment and indicators The analysis presents multiple indicators and not the h-index alone which is often seen in health sciences.	
10) Scrutinize indicators regularly and update them See principle 9.	

Preliminary conclusions: Does LM work as a consumer label?

—Not without explanations!

—Reliability of subjective interpretations of LM?

—Both we and our clients learned more about responsible metrics from the consumer label!

Further questions: Should LM be updated?

—Emphasize division of responsibilities?

– E.g. principle 2, “Measure performance against the research missions of the institution, group or researcher.”

—How should the concepts be interpreted?

– E.g. principle 9, “Recognize the systemic effects of assessment and indicators.”

Reference list

1. Hicks, D., Wouters, P., Waltman, L., de Rijcke, S. & Rafols, I. Bibliometrics: The Leiden Manifest for Research Metrics. *Nature* **520**, 429–431 (2015).
2. Hicks, D., Wouters, P., Waltman, L., de Rijcke, S. & Rafols, I. Leiden Manifesto for research metrics: Blog. Available at: <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/blog>. (Accessed: 6th August 2017).
3. Wildgaard, L., Andersern, J. P., Larsen, K. S., Price, A. & Gauffriau, M. *Can we implement the Leiden Manifesto principles in our daily work with research indicators?* (2016).
4. Hammarfelt, B. & Rushforth, A. D. *Indicators as judgment devices: Citizen bibliometrics in biomedicine and economics.* (2016).

